

IPBES BBA Chapter 4 – Paper selection to identify approaches and families of methods that are addressing biodiversity impacts / IPBES business and biodiversity assessment (Section 4.2)

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Description

This data management report pertains to the IPBES business and biodiversity assessment. In Chapter 4, experts selected 31 key papers based on their relevance in the field, drawing on their expert judgment. These papers were identified across a range of topical areas—including life cycle assessment, environmental impact assessment, ecosystem services, and other related approaches and reviews—and were used to identify different families of methods addressing biodiversity impacts. While the insights from this literature review helped shape the preliminary delineation of these families and approaches in Chapter 4, the final delineation was significantly refined and expanded through discussions of the outcomes within Chapter 4 and with experts from Chapters 2 and 3. The final classification reflects a synthesis of both evidence-based literature and expert consensus.

Protocol

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Expert selection of papers
- **Exact Search Date:** 18 September 2023 to 20 October 2023
- **Key papers:** 31 key papers (A)

Treatment applied: Expert knowledge was used to select 31 key papers.

- **Location and format of data (A):** IPBES_BBA_4.2_2024_(A)

Additional files

ID	Name	File Type	Size	Description
A	IPBES_BBA_4.2_07-2024_(A)	.csv	10 KB	List of 31 key papers